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Research Paper

Formulation And Evaluation of An Eco-Friendly Cockroach Repellent Spray Using Essential Oils: A Sustainable Alternative to Conventional Pesticides

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ABSTRACT

This study explores formulating and evaluating an eco-friendly cockroach-repellent spray using essential oils as a sustainable alternative to conventional chemical pesticides. The growing concerns over synthetic insecticides' health and environmental risks have driven the need for natural, non-toxic pest control solutions. This research focuses on developing a plant-based repellent that effectively prevents cockroaches while minimizing ecological impact. The formulation process involves selecting essential oils known for their insect-repelling properties, such as clove, Tulsi, and vetiver. These oils were blended with a suitable carrier and emulsifying agents to ensure proper dispersion and effectiveness. The repellent's efficacy was tested through controlled laboratory experiments, where the formulation was applied to cockroach-infested areas. Observations were made on the insects' behavior, repellent activity, and duration of effectiveness. The findings revealed that the formulated spray successfully repelled cockroaches, with higher concentrations of essential oils demonstrating greater efficacy. The repellent was found to be non-toxic and safe for human exposure, making it a viable alternative to synthetic pesticides. Additionally, the study highlighted the advantages of using essential oil-based formulations, including biodegradability, sustainability, and reduced risk of insecticide resistance. The study concludes that essential oil-based repellents can serve as an effective and environment friendly solution for cockroach control. Further research is recommended to optimize the formulation and assess its long-term effectiveness in real-world applications.

INTRODUCTION

Cockroaches are among the most common household pests and are known to act as vectors for

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various pathogenic microorganisms, contributing to food contamination and the spread of diseases¹. Their presence in domestic environments is associated with poor hygiene, allergic reactions, and respiratory disorders². Conventional chemical insecticides are widely used for cockroach control; however, their continuous usage has raised serious concerns due to toxicity, environmental pollution, and the development of insect resistance³.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the development of eco-friendly and sustainable pest control methods. Plant-based products, particularly essential oils, have gained attention due to their biodegradability, low toxicity, and broad-spectrum biological activities⁴. Essential oils derived from medicinal plants possess insecticidal, repellent, antimicrobial, and antioxidant properties, making them promising alternatives to synthetic pesticides⁵.

Among these, *Syzygium aromaticum* (clove) is rich in eugenol, a bioactive compound known for its strong insecticidal and repellent properties⁶. *Chrysopogon zizanioides* (vetiver) produces essential oil with long-lasting repellent activity due to its low volatility⁷. *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (tulsi) contains various phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, phenolics, and terpenoids, which contribute to its antimicrobial and insect-repellent effects⁸. Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of these plant-derived oils against various insect species, including cockroaches⁹⁻¹¹. Despite the proven potential of individual essential oils, there is limited research on their combined formulation and evaluation as a stable, effective cockroach repellent spray¹². The synergistic effect of multiple essential oils may enhance repellency and prolong activity while maintaining safety for human use.

Therefore, the present study aims to formulate and evaluate an eco-friendly cockroach repellent spray using essential oils of clove, tulsi, and vetiver as a

sustainable alternative to conventional chemical pesticides.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Fresh leaves of *Ocimum tenuiflorum*, dried flower buds of *Syzygium aromaticum*, and roots of *Chrysopogon zizanioides* were used for the study. Ethanol, distilled water, vinegar, lecithin, citric acid, ascorbic acid, and castor oil were used as reagents. All chemicals used were of analytical grade.¹⁴

Collection and Authentication

Leaves of *Ocimum tenuiflorum* were collected from local areas of Wayanad, Kerala. The plant material was authenticated by a qualified botanist from the Department of Botany, St. Mary's College, Sulthan Bathery.

Extraction of Plant Material

The collected plant materials were shade-dried and powdered.

- **Hydro-distillation:**

Dried clove buds and vetiver roots (100 g each) were subjected to hydro-distillation for 4–6 h using a round-bottom flask. The essential oils obtained were collected and stored in airtight containers.^{34,36}

- **Soxhlet extraction:**

Powdered leaves of *Ocimum tenuiflorum* were extracted using ethanol in a Soxhlet apparatus until complete extraction. The extract was collected and preserved for further analysis.¹⁸

Phytochemical Screening

The extracts were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening for the detection of phenolic compounds, phytosterols, triterpenoids, and eugenol using standard chemical tests such as ferric chloride test, gelatin test, lead acetate test, Liebermann–Burchard test, Salkowski test,

bromine water test, and potassium permanganate test.^{17,18}

Formulation of Cockroach Repellent Spray

The repellent spray was prepared as an emulsion using aqueous and oil phases.

- **Aqueous phase:**

Distilled water (50 ml) containing citric acid (0.1 g) and ascorbic acid (0.05 g) was mixed with tulsi extract (5 ml) and vinegar (5 ml).

- **Oil phase:**

Clove oil (5 ml), vetiver oil (5 ml), castor oil (5 drops), and lecithin (1 ml) were mixed thoroughly. The oil phase was slowly added to the aqueous phase with continuous stirring to form a stable emulsion. The final volume was adjusted to 100 ml using distilled water.⁴⁴

Evaluation of Repellent Activity

Fig1: Dried clove buds

Fig2: Dried vetiver roots

Fig 3: Tulsi leaves

2. Microscopic evaluation

Microscopic analysis revealed the presence of characteristic anatomical features such as oil glands in clove, parenchymatous cells with oil globules in vetiver, and glandular trichomes in tulsi leaves.

Repellent activity was evaluated using a cardboard box method. The box was divided into treated and control areas. The formulation was sprayed on the treated side, while the control remained untreated. Ten cockroaches were introduced into the box, and observations were recorded at 1, 6, 24, and 48 h intervals based on their distribution.^{40,41}

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Results

1. Macroscopic evaluation

Macroscopic evaluation confirmed the identity of plant materials based on their characteristic features. Clove buds were dark brown with a strong aroma, vetiver roots were fibrous with an earthy odor, and tulsi leaves were green, aromatic, and ovate in shape.

Fig 4: TS of Vetiver root

Fig 5: TS of clove buds

Fig 6: TS of Tulsi leaf

3. Phytochemical screening

Phytochemical screening indicated the presence of phenolic compounds, phytosterols, triterpenoids,

and eugenol in the extracts, confirming their potential biological activity. The formulated spray was physically stable with no phase separation observed during the study period.

Table1: Phytochemical screening tests

S L N O	CHEMICAL TESTS	INFERENCES
I. Test For Phenolic Compounds		
1	Ferric chloride test	+
2	Gelatin Test	+
3	Lead Acetate Test	+
4	Alkaline Reagent Test	+
5	Shinoda Test	+
II. Test for phytosterols and triterpenoids		
1	Liebermann's Burchard Test	+
2	Salkowski Test	+
III. Test for Eugenol		
1	Ferric Chloride Test	+
2	Potassium permanganate Test	+
3	Bromine Water Test	+

4. Evaluation of formulation

In the repellency test, cockroaches showed a clear tendency to avoid the treated area. At 1 h, initial

movement towards the control area was observed, and by 24–48 h, most cockroaches remained in the control section, indicating significant repellent activity.

DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate that the formulated herbal spray possesses effective cockroach repellent activity. The presence of eugenol in clove oil contributes to strong insecticidal and neurotoxic effects. Vetiver oil provides prolonged action due to its low volatility, while tulsi enhances the repellent effect through its phytoconstituents such as flavonoids and terpenoids.

The synergistic effect of these essential oils plays a key role in improving the overall efficacy of the formulation. Compared to synthetic insecticides, the developed formulation is eco-friendly, biodegradable, and safe for human use.

These findings support the potential application of plant-based formulations as sustainable alternatives for household pest control.

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